

Potassium Chromate and Potassium Dichromate as Light-filters and the Constitution of Chromic Acid from Absorption Measurements.

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The problem of obtaining suitable light-filters for isolating different spectral regions is in an unsatisfactory condition and our knowledge regarding the solution-filters appears to be meagre. The so-called monochromatic filters are seldom completely opaque to the other spectral regions. Quantitative investigation of filters is therefore of great importance in photochemistry.

In this communication, we have studied the absorption of potassium chromate and dichromate solutions of different concentrations in various regions of the visible spectrum. The use of solutions of potassium chromate in cutting off ultra-violet rays beyond 3660Å has been recommended. 0.001 Normal aqueous solution of potassium chromate in a quartz or uviol glass cell of 1 cm. thickness is said to absorb the mercury line 3660 Å. Wood (*Physical Optics*, 1914, p. 15) describes the use of potassium dichromate for the transmission of the green and the two yellow lines. No quantitative data, however, are available. A combination of cobalt glass and a saturated solution of potassium dichromate for the transmission of infra-red rays has been used. In a recent communication, Bhattacharya and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 877) have shown that the filter consisting of a saturated solution of potassium dichromate in a cobalt-glass cell of 1 cm. thickness cuts off all visible and ultra-violet radiations and transmits infra-red radiations of wave-length 8500Å.

In the following tables are given our absorption measurements for both potassium chromate and dichromate in the different regions of visible spectrum. The absorption has been determined by a Hilger Nutting's spectro-photometer using a quartz cell of 1 cm. thickness. The results have been expressed as extinction coefficients. We have also calculated the percentage transmission in the various regions of the visible spectrum.

TABLE I.

Absorption measurements of Potassium chromate.

	λ - wave-length in $\text{\AA}$.							ϵ - extinction coefficient.
(1) Concentration = 5.5 N.								
λ	... 6700	6500	6200	5800	5600	5400	5360	5275
ϵ	... 0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.28	0.48	0.61
λ	... 5200	5150	5000	4850	4600	4400	4290	4000
ϵ	... 1.68	∞						
(2) Concentration = 2 N.								
λ	... 6700	6600	6200	5800	5600	5400	5150	
ϵ	... 0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.26	1.04	
λ	... 4950	4800	4600	4400	4200	4000		
ϵ	... ∞	∞	∞	∞	∞	∞		
(3) Concentration = N.								
λ	... 6700	6500	6200	5800	5600	5400	5200	
ϵ	... 0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.19	0.26	
λ	... 5150	5000	4950	4800	4600	4200	4000	
ϵ	... 0.44	0.61	∞	∞	∞	∞	∞	
(4) Concentration = 0.1 N.								
λ	... 6700	6500	6200	5800	5600	5400	5150	
ϵ	... 0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.08	
λ	... 4950	4800	4600	4400	4200	4000		
ϵ	... 0.85	1.10	∞	∞	∞	∞		
(5) Concentration = 0.01 N.								
λ	... 6700	6500	6200	5800	5600	5400	5150	
ϵ	... 0.08	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
λ	... 4950	4800	4600	4450	4300	4200	4000	
ϵ	... 0.06	0.38	0.58	0.88	∞	∞	∞	
(6) Concentration = 0.001 N.								
λ	... 6700	6500	6200	5800	5600	5400	5150	
ϵ	... 0.06	0.06	0.06	0.08	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
λ	... 4950	4800	4600	4400	4200	4000		
ϵ	... 0.06	0.12	0.16	0.28	—	—		

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It will be observed from these results that with increasing concentration of potassium chromate, the absorption increases towards higher wave-lengths. For the saturated solution of potassium chromate (5.5 N) there is complete absorption for the wave-lengths shorter than 5150Å, while for greater wave-lengths, there is very little absorption. Thus there is sharp line of division between absorbed and transmitted part of the spectrum. This makes potassium chromate a very suitable light-filter, although its transmission range is large, extending from 5150-7000Å for visible region. But for whatever part it is transmitting, it practically causes no loss of intensity and this is highly advantageous from the viewpoint of a suitable filter. It has been observed by us that the combination of a saturated solution of K_2CrO_4 with cobalt glass behaves practically in the same way as the combination of cobalt glass with the saturated solution of potassium dichromate, which transmits only infra-red. Cobalt glass has high absorption for all the wave-lengths, longer than blue and is nowhere completely transparent for shorter wave-lengths. By using the glass of suitable thickness (about 0.5 cm.) practically all wave-lengths longer than blue are absorbed completely, and because the saturated solutions of both potassium chromate and dichromate have complete absorption for the wave-lengths shorter than blue and also for ultra-violet, the combination of cobalt glass either with potassium chromate or dichromate offers itself as a suitable filter for infra-red radiations. For the concentrations 2 N, N, 0.1N, 0.01N and 0.001 N, the regions shorter than 4950Å, 4950Å, 4600Å, 4300Å, 4000Å respectively are completely absorbed. Hence these concentrations can be used for the transmission of wave-lengths greater than those mentioned above. In all the cases the ultra-violet region is completely cut off. When the total visible spectrum is desirable, the use of potassium chromate of concentration 0.001 N is advisable. Thus the following results are obtained.

TABLE II.

K_2CrO_4 saturated + cobalt glass (0.5 cm. thick) — transmits infra-red radiations		
Saturated solution of K_2CrO_4 — cuts off wave-lengths shorter than		5150Å.
2 N solution of K_2CrO_4 .	do	4950Å.
N solution of K_2CrO_4 .	do	4950Å.
0.1 N solution of K_2CrO_4 .	do	4600Å.
0.01 N solution of K_2CrO_4 .	do	4300Å.
0.001 N solution of K_2CrO_4 .	do	4000Å.

TABLE III.

λ = wave-length in Å. ϵ = extinction coefficient.

Absorption measurements of Potassium dichromate.

(1) Concentration 1.17 N (saturated solution at 34°).

λ ...	6700	6500	6200	5800	5750	5675	5600
ϵ ...	0.18	0.18	0.30	0.38	0.56	1.06	2.40
λ ...	5500	5200	4800	4600	4400	4200	4000
ϵ ...	∞						

(2) Concentration = 0.1 N.

λ ...	6700	6500	6200	5800	5600	5400	5300
ϵ ...	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.12	0.20	1.20	2.02
λ ...	5275	5250	5200	4800	4600	4400	4000
ϵ ...	2.22	3.72	∞	∞	∞	∞	∞

(3) Concentration = 0.01 N.

λ ...	6700	6500	6200	5800	5600	5400	5100
ϵ ...	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.12	0.16	0.53
λ ...	4950	4750	4650	4600	4400	4200	4000
ϵ ...	0.99	1.42	2.14	∞	∞	∞	∞

(4) Concentration = 0.001 N.

λ ...	6700	6500	6200	5800	5600	5400	5100
ϵ ...	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.08
λ ...	4950	4800	4600	4450	4300	4150	4000
ϵ ...	0.12	0.16	0.20	0.27	0.28	—	—

It will be observed that a saturated solution of potassium dichromate absorbs completely all the wave-lengths shorter than 5600 Å. Thus the filter (conc. 1.17 N) is useful when only the rays of wave-length greater than 5600 Å are to be used. The concentrations 0.1 N, 0.01 N and 0.001 N of potassium chromate absorb completely the wave-lengths shorter than 5200 Å, 4600 Å and 4000 Å respectively. Hence when the rays of wave-lengths greater than those mentioned above are to be transmitted, the given concentrations of the solution of potassium dichromate will be found convenient.

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TABLE IV.

Filter.	Radiations absorbed.
$K_2Cr_2O_7$, saturated + cobalt glass (0.5 cm. thick).	Visible and ultra-violet.
Normal solution of $K_2Cr_2O_7$,	Shorter than 5600 Å
0.1 N "	" 5200 Å
0.01 N "	" 4600 Å
0.001 N "	" 4000 Å

For the same concentration, potassium dichromate has a higher absorption than potassium chromate. This will be evident from the comparative table given below.

TABLE V.

Concentration.	Region of complete absorption.	
	K_2CrO_4	$K_2Cr_2O_7$
5.5 N	5150 Å	—
2 N	4950 Å	—
1.0 N	4950 Å	5600 Å
0.1 N	4600 Å	5200 Å
0.01 N	4300 Å	4600 Å
0.001 N	4000 Å	4000 Å

The maximum absorption obtained in the case of K_2CrO_4 is up to the limit of 5150 Å only, while it extends as far as 5600 Å in case of $K_2Cr_2O_7$. Thus the filter $K_2Cr_2O_7$ is more useful than K_2CrO_4 for cutting off the major part of the visible spectrum especially beyond yellow. But it has the disadvantage over potassium chromate in that it has a much higher absorption in larger wavelengths than potassium chromate. Thus the intensity of the transmitted light is diminished to a greater extent than with K_2CrO_4 solution of the same concentration.

Hantzsch (*Z. physikal Chem.*, 1910, 72, 862) has also determined the molecular extinction coefficient of solutions of potassium chromate and dichromate for 5460 Å, 4860 Å and 4360 Å. His results show that the molecular extinction coefficients decrease slightly on dilution of the salts, whilst our measurements show that the molecular extinction coefficients increase markedly with dilution. We

have obtained similar results with several cupric salts, which also do not obey Beer's law. Moreover, the details of the experimental procedure of Hantzsch are not recorded in his paper and hence it is impossible to explain the discrepancy between his and our results. We have repeated our measurements and we have observed that our results are reproducible.

We now proceed to determine the percentage transmission of light in various regions of visible spectrum for aqueous solutions of different concentrations of potassium chromate and potassium dichromate. We have used a quartz cell 1 cm. thick. According to Lambert's law, the fraction of the incident light, which is absorbed by a medium of a definite thickness is independent of the initial intensity. According to this law, the absorption increases in geometrical progression as the thickness increases in arithmetical progression. Consider an absorbing medium of thickness l and let I_x be the intensity of the light after its passage through the length x of the medium. The decrease in intensity on passing through a thin layer dx of the medium is given by the expression

$$-dI = kI_x dx \quad \dots (i)$$

where k is generally designated as the constant or coefficient of absorption. On integration we get

$$I = I_0 e^{-kl}$$

$$\text{or} \quad \log \frac{I}{I_0} = -kl \quad \dots (ii)$$

where I represents the intensity of the emergent light. These results can be written in the form

$$I = I_0 10^{-El}$$

where E is the extinction coefficient. Hence percentage transmission is given by

$$\frac{100 \times I}{I_0} = \frac{1}{10^{El}} \times 100;$$

but in our case $l=1$ cm. Therefore percentage transmission is given by

$$\frac{1}{10^E} \times 100 \quad \dots (iii)$$

This is the relation that we have used in determining the percentage transmission of the solutions of potassium chromate and dichromate.

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TABLE VI.
Percentage transmission of K_2CrO_4 .

λ (Å)	Concentrations :					
	5.5 N	2.0 N	1.0 N	0.1 N	0.01 N	0.001 N
4000	0	0	0	0	0	—
4200	0	0	0	0	0	—
4400	0	0	0	0	13.0	54.9
4600	0	0	0	0	26.9	69.1
4800	0	0	0	7.9	41.7	75.6
4950	0	0	0	44.6	87.1	87.1
5150	0	9.1	64.9	83.1	87.1	87.1
5400	52.4	55.0	64.5	85.1	87.1	87.1
5600	83.1	83.1	83.1	85.1	87.1	87.1
5800	83.1	83.1	83.1	85.1	87.1	87.1
6200	83.1	83.1	83.1	85.1	87.1	87.1
6500	83.1	83.1	83.1	85.1	87.1	87.1
6700	83.1	83.1	83.1	85.1	87.1	87.1

TABLE VII.
Percentage transmission of $K_2Cr_2O_7$.

λ (Å)	Concentrations :			
	1.17 N	0.1 N	0.01 N	0.001 N
4000	0	0	0	—
4300	0	0	0	—
4400	0	0	0	53.7
4600	0	0	0	69.1
4800	0	0	3.8	69.1
4950	0	0	10.2	75.6
5150	0	0	30.2	83.1
5225	0	0	—	—
5300	0	0.95	—	—
5400	0	6.3	69.1	89.1
5550	0	—	—	—
5600	0.39	63.1	75.6	91.2
5675	8.7	—	—	—
5800	41.6	75.8	79.4	93.3
6200	63.1	83.1	81.2	93.3
6500	66.0	83.1	83.1	93.3
6700	66.0	83.1	85.1	93.3

It has been shown by Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1921, 121, 99; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 6, 585) and by Bhagwat and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 781) that chromic acid exists mainly as H_2CrO_4 and potassium dichromate exists in solution chiefly as KHCrO_4 in dilute solutions. We have drawn the curves representing absorption of radiations of definite wave-lengths at different concentrations for both potassium chromate and dichromate. It has been observed that for high concentrations, the nature of the curves is widely different but as the concentration falls, the similarity of the curves is marked. Hence it appears that in very dilute solutions both chromate and dichromate behave similarly and hence chromic acid mainly exists as H_2CrO_4 in dilute solutions. Moreover it will be clear from the absorption data that Beer's law is not applicable. Beer's law is a molecular characteristic and appears to be valid for all solutions in which the molecular species undergo no fundamental change on dilution. In other words, as long as the molecular constitution is unchanged, absorption must be proportional to dilution. But this is not at all true for both the solutions of potassium chromate and dichromate. In spite of the change of concentration from 1.0 N to 0.001N, there is practically the same absorption for high wave-lengths of visible spectrum. The explanation as to the formation of hydrated molecules of the type $\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4 \cdot n \text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot n \text{H}_2\text{O}$, thus decreasing the actual water-content and increasing the concentration of the solution, appears unsatisfactory, when we consider the consistency of absorption results for such a wide range of concentration as 1.0 N—0.001 N. It is, therefore, clear that with the change of concentration, there is actually change in the molecular species. We are of the opinion that in concentrated solutions, there is an equilibrium of the type

and this equilibrium shifts to the side of H_2CrO_4 on dilution. The colour of the saturated solution of potassium dichromate is red, which on dilution becomes orange and finally yellow, that is, it assumes the colour of the chromate. A saturated solution of potassium chromate has an orange tinge. It appears, therefore, that concentrated solutions of chromic acid and dichromates, may contain $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and HCr_2O_7^- ions but in dilute solutions HCrO_4^- and CrO_4^{2-} ions predominate.

Summary.

(1) The absorption and percentage transmission for aqueous solutions of potassium chromate and potassium dichromate of various concentrations have been determined. It has been observed that a saturated solution of potassium chromate (5.5 *N*) transmits wave-lengths longer than 5150Å. A saturated solution of potassium dichromate can conveniently be used to cut off all the wave-lengths shorter than 5600Å.

(2) In very dilute solutions, chromates and dichromates of potassium behave similarly, from the viewpoint of light absorption and hence chromic acid in dilute solution appears to exist mainly as $\overset{+}{H}HCrO_4'$ and CrO_4'' ions and dichromates as $HCrO_4'$ and CrO_4'' ions.

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